

UP2030

Urban Planning and design ready for 2030

D5.5 - Guidelines for economic valuations & assessment of financial instruments for spatial interventions 2

SCAN QR CODE

About UP2030:

UP2030 is dedicated to aiding cities in achieving climate neutrality through enhanced urban planning and design. The project introduces the innovative 5UP approach to support city stakeholders and local authorities in integrating climate-neutral strategies into their everyday actions and long-term planning. Focused on promoting spatial justice and inclusive participation, UP2030 empowers communities and local governments to become agents of change, driving socio-technical transitions that enhance urban liveability and sustainability. The project's strategy aims to produce actionable insights and scalable solutions for urban environments, prioritizing resilience, equity, and sustainable urban development.

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Abstract	<p>This deliverable presents two practical tools developed by GGGI under Task 5.3 of the UP2030 project to support European municipalities in advancing climate-neutral interventions: the Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA) Guide and the Green Finance (GF) Guide. The CBA Guide assists municipalities in selecting from 20 open-access cost-benefit analysis tools through a user-friendly questionnaire that tailors recommendations to project type, data availability, and resource constraints. The GF Guide provides a structured overview of over 100 financing instruments, more than 70 case studies, and international funding and technical assistance programmes, enabling cities to identify and search for suitable financing mechanisms through filters. Both guides were presented to and refined with UP2030 city stakeholders through workshops, ensuring alignment with local needs. Currently available in Excel format, the guides will be integrated into the UP2030 Service Platform in a web-based format by late 2025, improving accessibility and replication across cities. Together, these tools help cities to evaluate the economic viability and co-benefits of climate projects, mobilise finance, and scale interventions, contributing to the broader objectives of the EU Mission for Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities.</p>			

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Executive summary

This deliverable presents two practical guides developed by the Global Green Growth Institute (GGGI) under Task 5.3 of the UP2030 project: the Green Finance (GF) Guide and the Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA) Guide. These tools aim to support European municipalities in planning, financing, and scaling up climate interventions by improving access to financial instruments and strengthening economic analysis capabilities.

The GF Guide provides a structured overview of over 100 financial instruments, 70+ case studies, and key international finance providers, enabling cities to identify and assess suitable funding mechanisms. Its modular design allows users to filter and navigate content based on sector, project type, financing modality, and risk/readiness levels.

The CBA Guide supports municipal decision-making by helping users select from 20 open-access tools for conducting cost-benefit assessments of climate projects. Through a user-friendly questionnaire, cities receive tailored tool recommendations and guidance on data requirements and resource needs.

Both guides were co-developed with city input through workshops and surveys, ensuring alignment with real-world needs and challenges. They are currently available in Excel format and will be integrated into the UP2030 Service Platform in an interactive web-based format by the third quarter of 2025, enhancing accessibility and replicability across cities.

Together, these tools will help cities, within the UP2030 project and beyond, to support the planning and upscaling of climate-neutral interventions by improving financial planning through economic evaluation of projects and assessing options for potential financing sources.

Content alignment with other UP2030 deliverables

The UP2030 project fosters exchange and cooperation among partners and deliverables beyond the WP structures. Therefore, the content of this document has been developed in alignment with WP5 leaders and task leaders from WP5, WP2, and the Strategy and Learning Taskforce. The following table lists the deliverables (D) and milestones (Mil.) that were input for this present document and the upcoming ones that could benefit from the content presented below.

Input from	Contributes to
D5.4 Guidelines for economic valuations & assessment of financial instruments for spatial interventions 1	D4.7 Report on Strategic Learning in City Twinning Programmes
D5.2 Analysis and Recommendations for Transformative Governance and Policy 2	D5.2 Analysis and Recommendations for Transformative Governance and Policy 2
D3.2 Transformative Pathways Roadmaps: Strategic Integration of Solutions and Interoperability 2	D5.3 UP2030 Service platform D5.7 Online Learning Programme materials
Mil.10 Cities run third workshop on action Mil.14 Cities run second workshop on upscale	Mil.16 Service platform up operative Mil.15 Training programme successful delivery

This deliverable is the final report on the guides GGGI has prepared for cities on economic valuations and on financial instruments as part of Task 5.3, under WP5. The report aims to provide information to UP2030 partners and European city municipality officials (UP2030 pilot cities and beyond) about the two guides GGGI developed: (i) the GF Guide on financial measures (financial instruments, sources of finance and funding) and (ii) a CBA Guide. GGGI developed the Guides in Excel format, which – in collaboration with ICLEI Europe – will be integrated onto the UP2030 service platform in a web-based format. Mission Cities can use the Guides to inform the preparation of their Climate Action Plans and Climate-Neutral Investment Plans, developed in the framework of the European Union's *100 Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities by 2030* Mission and within the efforts of NetZeroCities (NZN). The tools support cities in assessing the economic and co-benefits of proposed interventions and in identifying and evaluating financing sources and instruments to mobilise investment for their climate neutrality commitments.

Acronyms

Acronym	Full name
CBA	Cost-Benefit Analysis
D	Deliverable
D5.4	D5.4 - Guidelines for economic valuations & assessment of financial instruments for spatial interventions
EPC	Energy Performance Contracts
EU	European Union
GF	Green Finance
GGGI	Global Green Growth Institute
ICLEI	ICLEI - Local Governments for Sustainability
LAA	Learning Action Alliance
LVC	Land Value Capture
M	Month
MBI	Market-Based Instrument
Mil	Milestone
MOOC	Massive Open Online Course
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
NZC	NetZeroCities
N/A	Not Applicable
ODA	Official Development Assistance
OSR	Own Source Revenue
PPP	Public-private partnership
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
TA	Technical Assistance
UIC	Universitat Internacional de Catalunya
VSL	Value of Statistical Life
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and scope

This report is a key deliverable of the Task 5.3 "Financing the transition" of the UP2030 project, within WP5 that aims to support European cities in scaling up their climate interventions. Building on the groundwork laid out in "D5.4 — Guidelines for economic valuations & assessment of financial instruments for spatial interventions 1", this report introduces and presents the two practical guides developed to support cities planning and upscaling efforts: the two guides on Green Finance (GF) and Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA).

The objective of Task 5.3 has been to help cities accelerate and upscale their climate action by providing them with tailored guidance in two critical areas: first, by supporting cities in assessing the costs and benefits of different climate interventions and selecting appropriate CBA tools to underpin informed decision-making. Second, by equipping them with practical knowledge about available financing and funding options and guiding them in leveraging diverse financial instruments to mobilise the necessary resources for their climate initiatives.

To achieve these goals, the Global Green Growth Institute (GGGI) developed two targeted Guides:

1. **CBA Guide:** This Guide offers practical support for cities to carry out economic assessments of climate interventions. It helps them choose suitable CBA tools, access relevant data sources, and structure analyses that align with their specific needs.
2. **GF Guide:** This Guide helps cities navigate the landscape of climate finance by mapping financing instruments, mechanisms, and relevant stakeholders. It provides insights into building robust business cases, combining innovative financial instruments, and accessing technical assistance (TA).

The Guides were developed based on the needs assessments conducted with cities under the UP2030 project (including under WP2), as well as through targeted surveys, workshops, and a supporting literature review and benchmark analysis (see Section 2.3). This ensured that both Guides are firmly grounded in theory while tailored to the real-world needs of cities.

Three city engagements activities were conducted by the consortium and GGGI with the aim to understand the barriers and challenges pilot cities face and validate literature findings:

1. Workshops on needs and barriers identification: conducted by WP2 partners with the support of cities' local liaison partners (under T2.3 "City and stakeholder engagement for the identification of needs for upgrading, barriers and drivers of change"), to identify cities' needs, barriers, and opportunities for urban climate interventions. (M3-M6)
2. Survey on financing needs and barriers: conducted by GGGI (in WP5 under T5.3), building on the results of the Workshops on needs identification, the project team sent out a survey to pilot cities in order to gather detailed insights on how cities finance their climate initiatives, budgetary and fiscal stability, the challenges faced, and strategies employed to assess costs and benefits and mobilise finance and funding. (M11)
3. Focused workshops on financing, CBA and the guides: conducted by GGGI (in WP5 under T5.3), they were held to gain a deeper understanding of cities' financing barriers, needs, and preferences for guide functionalities, along with cities' needs in relation to estimating costs

and benefits. The workshop also provided valuable insights for the development of the Guides. (M15)

Figure 1 summarises the timeline and key steps of the pilot city engagements, including the workshops in needs and barrier identification, the surveys, and the focused workshops on the Guide's functionalities.

Figure 1: The structure of pilot city engagements and their contribution to the guides

This report presents the final outputs of Task 5.3 by:

- Presenting the completed CBA and GF Guides, including their content, practical applications, and the support they offer to cities – according to their current Excel-based format at the writing of this report.
- Including a hands-on user manual in this report to both Guides.
- Outlining the next steps on dissemination and Guides integration into the UP2030 Service Platform (T5.2), ensuring that cities can access these resources in an interactive, web-based format.

These resources will be available beyond the end of the project for replicating cities to help them advance their climate ambitions from concept to implementation.

1.2 Document structure

The document is organised as follows:

- ❖ Section 1 — Introduction: description of the purpose and scope of the document and its structure
- ❖ Section 2 — Background: summary of the project context and the role of the developed Guides
- ❖ Section 3 — Cost-Benefit Analysis Guide: description of the purpose, structure and functionalities of the CBA Guide
- ❖ Section 4 — Green Finance Guide: description of the purpose, structure and functionalities of the GF Guide

- ❖ Section 5 — Integration into the platform and sustainability
- ❖ Section 6 — Conclusion

1.3 [Glossary](#)

The following section collects the key terms that are used across the two Guides, based on the Guides' structure and content. They are not listed in their order of relevance, but in the order that the user might come across these terms when using the Excel-based Guides.

1.3.1 [General terms](#)

Financial instruments — In this Guide, we refer to financial instruments as a broad set of mechanisms and tools used to mobilise, allocate, or manage capital for investment. In the context of climate and urban development finance, these may include grants, loans, guarantees, equity, de-risking tools, results-based financing, or blended finance approaches — thus they may be repayable or non-repayable forms of finance. They can be provided by public, private, or philanthropic actors and are often tailored to specific project types, risk profiles, or investment readiness levels. Financial instruments may serve to leverage additional funding, reduce financial risks, or incentivise sustainable outcomes, depending on their structure and use.

Blended finance — Blended finance is a financing approach that strategically combines public or philanthropic funds (such as grants or development assistance) with private capital to mobilise additional investment for development goals, such as the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) or climate action. By using public funds to de-risk projects, blended finance makes investments more attractive to private actors while enabling larger-scale impact.

Innovative finance — Innovative finance includes mechanisms and solutions which increase the volume, efficiency, and effectiveness of financial flows, which mobilise, govern, or distribute funds beyond official development assistance (ODA). Innovative finance solutions create scalable and effective ways of channelling both private money from the global and local financial markets and public resources towards sustainable investments.

1.3.2 [Cost-Benefit Analysis Guide](#)

Cost-benefit analysis - A CBA is a systematic process for evaluating the financial implications of a project or decision by comparing the total expected costs against the total expected benefits, typically expressed in monetary terms. Benefits can be financial benefits, such as additional cash flows and cost savings, but also so-called co-benefits, such as improved environmental or health conditions at the society level.

1.3.3 [Green-Finance Guide](#)¹

Sector

Transportation and mobility — Systems and infrastructure enabling the movement of people and goods, including public transit, roads, cycling, and electric mobility.

Buildings and energy efficiency — Design, construction, and retrofitting of buildings to reduce energy consumption and improve performance.

Energy generation and systems — Production and distribution of energy from renewable and conventional sources, including grid infrastructure and storage.

¹ The terms are listed based on the filter categories of the GF Guide.

Water, waste, and wastewater — Management of water supply, sewage, stormwater, and solid waste (including recycling) to ensure sustainability and public health.

Urban development and management — Planning and governance of urban areas, focusing on infrastructure, services, housing, and liveability.

Green spaces and nature-based solutions — Use of natural systems (e.g., parks, wetlands) to address urban challenges like heat, flooding, and air quality.

Disaster risk management — Strategies and actions to reduce the impact of natural and human-made hazards, including preparedness, mitigation, and response systems.

Maturity

Mature — Evidence for implementation is high.

Emerging — Moderate evidence for implementation, instrument and mechanism is tried and tested.

Pilot — Low implementation status, limited evidence is available.

Instrument type

Debt — Debt instruments are agreements between a lender and a borrower in which the lender receives fixed payment(s), usually with interest. Borrowing can be done through bonds or bank loans, or other sources. These borrowed funds can come from either a private or public source.

Public — Public finance instruments refer to financial instruments directly issued or managed by public institutions (e.g., national governments, local governments, development banks, climate funds).

Equity — Equity finance is a type of financing that involves the purchase of a share in the ownership of a company or project. It is often called shareholders' equity or owners' equity on a balance sheet, and represents the amount of money that belongs to the owners of a business after all assets and liabilities have been accounted for.

Grant — Grants are non-repayable funds disbursed by the government or international financing institutions. The eligibility criteria are always defined by the donors.

Risk transfer or mitigation — Risk transfer or mitigation financing instruments are financial tools designed to reduce, share, or manage the financial risks associated with climate and green investments—especially those related to revenue uncertainty, project failure, or extreme events.

Market-based — Market-based instruments (MBIs) are financial or policy tools that use market signals and price mechanisms to encourage behaviour that supports environmental and climate goals.

Modality

Non-repayable — Instruments, such as grants, provided without the obligation to repay, typically used for public goods or to support early-stage initiatives.

Repayable — Instruments, such as loans or investments, that must be paid back, often with interest or returns, depending on the structure, terms and conditions set by the finance provider.

De-risking — Financial instruments like guarantees or insurance that reduce the risk for private investors, encouraging investment in high-risk or new markets.

Results-based — Financing tied to the achievement of specific outcomes or performance indicators, with disbursement made after pre-agreed results of climate activity are achieved and verified.

Source of finance

Public [Domestic] — Direct funding from national, regional, or local government budgets (within the country), including ministries, state agencies, and municipalities.

Public [International] — Finance from foreign governments or international public institutions, multilateral organisations, such as development banks or climate funds.

Public [Municipal own source revenue (OSR)] — Funds provided directly by a city or local government's budget, generated by own revenues, such as taxes, fees, or service charges.

Private — Funding from the private sector, including businesses, investors, or financial institutions or households. Types of instruments mobilising private finance include loans, equity, and direct investments made by corporations and households.

Mixed (public and private) — Blended finance combining public and private resources.

Category of blending

Structured funds and facilities — Collective investment vehicles pool financial resources from different investors in financial or nonfinancial assets, or both.

Insurance — Risk-transfer mechanisms that protect investors or projects from specific risks (e.g., weather events, political instability), making investments more attractive and bankable.

Grants — Grants are non-repayable funds disbursed by the government or international financing institutions. The eligibility criteria are always defined by the donors.

Loans and debt financing instruments — Money lent with the expectation of repayment, often with concessional (below-market) terms.

Guarantees — Risk-mitigation tools in which a public or development finance institution commits to cover losses if a borrower defaults, encouraging private lenders to finance riskier projects.

Outcome funding/ Results-based financing — Financing models where payment is made only upon delivery of agreed results or outcomes, aligning incentives and attracting private investment in social or environmental goals.

Equity financing — Equity finance is a type of financing that involves the purchase of a share in the ownership of a company or project. It is often called shareholders' equity or owners' equity on a balance sheet and represents the amount of money that belongs to the owners of a business after all assets and liabilities have been accounted for.

Not blending instrument — Financing instruments or mechanisms that cannot be blended.

Investment readiness and risk

Low risk, high readiness — The project is mature, well-structured, and highly bankable, with minimal risks across technical, financial, environmental, and social dimensions. Best suited for commercial financing instruments such as loans and equity investments, typically with low-risk appetite investors like commercial banks, institutional investors, and infrastructure funds.

Medium risk and readiness — The project shows moderate preparation and viability, but some uncertainties or barriers remain that may require targeted support. Best suited for blended finance solutions combining concessional loans, guarantees, or risk-sharing instruments with commercial capital, different types of bonds and public-private partnerships.

High risk, low readiness — The project is in an early or untested stage, with significant risks and limited readiness, requiring substantial development and risk mitigation. Best suited for grant funding, TA, or early-stage concessional capital and loans, typically from philanthropic donors, climate finance facilities, or international funds.

Case study type

Blending instruments — Includes case studies where multiple financing instruments were blended (mixed) to finance the project.

Innovative financial instruments — Includes case studies where innovative financial instruments were used (identified as innovative by GGGI).

Private finance — Includes case studies where private finance was utilised.

Type of assistance

Finance provision — Type of programme that provides capital and financing for different project stages (e.g. planning, implementation, maintenance).

Capacity building & technical assistance — Type of programme that provides TA in a form of knowledge or assistance, or capital that can be utilised for capacity building.

2 Background

2.1 Project context

UP2030 is an innovative action project supported by the European Union's Horizon Europe program. It aims to support cities in driving the socio-technical transitions required to meet their climate neutrality targets by leveraging urban planning and design. Within the project, city stakeholders and local authorities are supported and guided to put neutrality and resilience on the map in their day-to-day actions and strategic decisions.

The UP2030 consortium comprises 10+1 cities: Belfast, Budapest, Granollers, Istanbul, Lisbon, Milan, Muenster, Rotterdam, Thessaloniki, and Zagreb, with Rio de Janeiro as an observer city (see Figure 2). These pilot cities operationalise and co-develop the 5UP methodology and tools through their demonstration projects.

Figure 2: Pilot cities of the UP2030 HE project (UP2030, 2023)

2.2 The role of CBA and finance within UP2030

To achieve the objectives of the project, an innovative methodology, the UP2030 project develops and applies the so-called 5UP-approach (Figure 3) for activating cities and their stakeholders through five interlinked phases and the co-development and implementation of science-based, yet practical, tools, and methods (Fernandez 2023).

Figure 3: UP2030 methodological framework ("5UP")

- UP-dating, those policies, codes, and regulations that need to be left behind to make room for the new vision;
- UP-skilling, through building the capacities of the entire city stakeholder ecosystem that shall deliver actions;
- UP-grading, through the development of solution prototypes (digital and physical) at selected neighbourhoods;
- UP-scaling, to achieve city-wide impact by shaping the enabling governance arrangements and matching project portfolios to financial resources;
- UP-taking, by engaging with the EU Mission of Climate-Neutral and Smart cities (hereinafter EU Mission) and sharing best practices across European cities.

Within UP2030, the WP5, "UP-SCALING — Implementation and mainstreaming through renewed policy development and decision-making" focuses on extending the solutions across scales and integrating across sectors, whilst also responding to updated needs by shaping governance arrangements and financial mechanisms. The analysis of costs and benefits of climate action projects can significantly assist urban decision-makers in working out the best strategy for using scarce economic resources for the most effective climate measures and help prioritise and design climate investments. Moreover, it can raise awareness of the benefits of climate interventions and gain political and social support and improve its potential to obtain finance. Finance has a central role in enabling city-wide implementation and replication of cities' pilot and demonstration initiatives, leading to a sustainable transition to a low-carbon, climate-resilient future.

2.3 Development of the finance Guides

The first report delivered by GGGI as part of the UP2030 project, the "D5.4 - Guidelines for economic valuations & assessment of financial instruments for spatial interventions" (hereinafter D5.4) presented a comprehensive needs assessment, including literature review and engagement with pilot cities, to identified key barriers European cities face in conducting economic assessments and obtaining finance for their climate actions (for more information on the needs assessment see D5.4) .

GGGI's research and engagement with UP2030 pilot cities highlighted that European cities face a complex array of barriers to financing climate action. These include regulatory and legal constraints such as borrowing limits and limited taxation powers, high municipal debt and low creditworthiness, as well as difficulties accessing private investment due to high upfront costs, unclear returns, and transaction complexities. Market risks, political uncertainties, and restrictive procurement processes further complicate financing efforts. Additionally, cities struggle with inadequate technical capacities to prepare bankable projects, a lack of integrated planning, and insufficient data to quantify costs, benefits, and co-benefits, which are considered key to building investor confidence. Institutional fragmentation and limited coordination across municipal departments exacerbate these challenges, while many funding schemes remain oriented toward national rather than local governments (see D5.4).

To overcome these obstacles, cities expressed needs for improved understanding, capacities and access to diverse financing sources, comprehensive business planning, innovative financial models such as public-private partnerships (PPPs), and to conduct cost-benefit analyses and develop investor-ready projects. Further details about the needs assessment and cities' feedback are summarised in D5.4. Based on needs and gaps identified, the development of the two Guides started with extensive desk research. The key resources and insights used for the Guides are outlined in D5.4.

To test and refine the Guide according to cities' need and to help UP2030 pilot cities prepare for their Upscaling workshops with their Learning and Action Alliances (Mil.14), 10 workshops were carried out throughout April and May 2025 with the 10 European pilot cities (Belfast, Budapest, Granollers, Istanbul, Lisbon, Milan, Muenster, Rotterdam, Thessaloniki, and Zagreb). During these workshops, GGGI presented the latest versions of both Guides — explaining their objectives, high-level content and how to use them. The agenda for all city workshops included an introduction and discussion of goals (10'), applying the CBA Guide to find suitable CBA tools for the prototype (20'), using the GF Guide to identify recommended instruments for the prototype (20'), and concluding with Q&A and discussion (10'). At the same time, GGGI collected feedback from cities to improve the Guides as needed. In general, cities confirmed that the tools will be valuable during the planning phase of their current or planned projects. Still, given that most cities prepare a strategic document or guidance, they will not use these tools themselves but rather share them with the target users of their strategies and other municipal officers for use in the future.

Based on the feedback received during the workshops (comments during the workshops and Granollers providing written feedback after the workshop²), cities generally found the CBA Guide strategic and useful for strengthening the financial case for their urban projects (see Table 1). It was seen as a valuable tool to structure projects financially, integrate finance considerations into planning, and prepare business cases to attract investment. However, many cities noted, that in general, they face challenges related to data availability, quantifying adaptation benefits, and limited local capacity to conduct analyses. The GF Guide was appreciated for introducing a range of financing instruments and practical case studies. Cities found it particularly helpful for identifying funding options for retrofitting, nature-based solutions, and other climate-related projects. A few cities noted the complexity of the tool that was improved during the last stage of the development to make it more user-friendly and develop a more visual user manual (such as the video developed for the massive online open course (MOOC), under D5.7 Online Learning Programme materials). Table 1 summarises the more specific comments that were taken into account and addressed during the final stage of the development of the tools to improve the user experience, resolve bugs³, and better reflect the cities' needs.

² Granollers specifically asked for the option to provide feedback in a written form. All feedback received were considered and addressed adequately, regardless their format.

³ Bugs refer to a fault in the macro that prevent the Excel to produce the result.

Table 1: Key comments and takeaways of city workshops

City	Date of the workshop	Key comments	Solution
Belfast	16/04/2025	Found a few of bugs in the CBA Guide.	Bugs were solved.
Budapest	30/04/2025	The city does not have much experience with CBA calculations. They asked if the CBA Guide's sectors and their indicators could be harmonised with what the other UP2030 cities have been using (for example in the Healthy Streets Project).	The sectors and their indicators remained unchanged as the key objective was to use a categorisation that reflects the typology used in the included tools.
Granollers	15/04/2025	The city found a few of bugs and asked for further clarification regarding the use of the Guides.	The bugs were solved, and further clarifications were given to the city.
Istanbul	28/04/2025	Bugs were found in the CBA Guide and asked if the GF Guide's instruments can be updated by linking carbon reduction metrics to financial units.	Bugs were solved. The comment on linking financial units with carbon reduction metric is currently out of the scope of the Guide, but such criteria could be included in the future (especially for instruments such as green bonds, etc.)
Lisbon	06/05/2025	The city is struggling with quantifying the value of adaptation and were interested in CBA tools that could help them with this.	While the CBA Guide includes some tools focusing on adaptation, in general, there is a lack of such tools. As more of such tools are expected to be developed in the future, they could potentially be added to the CBA Guide after the project.
Milan	07/05/2025	They asked for clarification about how the Guides will be kept up to date after the project. They suggested promoting the CBA Guide for the private sector as well, as in many cases they will be support municipalities. In relation to the GF Guide, they asked to add information to the international financing programmes on what the programme's finance could be used for.	In relation to the sustainability of the Guides see Section 5. The Guides will be open-source and free to use for both the public and private sector. Information was added to the international financing programmes on what the finance can be used for.
Muenster	28/04/2025	For the CBA Guide, the city was interested in how it will be kept up to date after the end of the project. In relation to the GF Guide, they asked for a short summary of the tool and a step-by-step guide that they could refer to.	In relation to the sustainability of the Guides see Section 5. A short summary and a step-by-step guide of the Guides were sent out after the meeting. They were also added to the Guides' "Intro" worksheets.
Rotterdam	17/04/2025	The city was interested in what CBA tools could be applied at a	The CBA Guide includes tools that can be used at a neighbourhood level and also tools that consider

		neighbourhood level and what tools are suitable to calculate social aspects.	social aspects (mostly quantifiable aspects linked to inequality).
Thessaloniki	29/04/2025	Asked for a guide for the tools and a glossary.	Guides and glossaries were added.
Zagreb	09/05/2025	The city provided positive feedback and found the Guides helpful. No specific comments were made in relation to how the Guides could be improved.	N/A

During Learning Action Alliance (LAA) workshops, the cities have discussed how the CBA and GF Guides can be used by the cities and help to scale up the prototypes they have developed. The seven following pilot cities recorded the key takeaways in their Upscaling Phase reports:

- Budapest — Budapest plans to use the CBA and GF tools as planning guides for urban development. They will be shared through the Knowledge Centre platform. The city estimated the needed resources and potential funding sources for the next year.
- Granollers — Granollers is integrating a CBA and GF Guides into their urban planning prototype. While the tools weren't directly applicable at the current scale, they outlined a future financing plan with estimated costs, funding sources, and responsibilities. These will guide future neighbourhood development and be included in the final prototype to support strategic implementation.
- Istanbul — Istanbul recognises that local authorities alone will not be sufficient to implement the project. Therefore, presenting the project results and the Guides will support decision-making efforts for future projections. Raising awareness about rooftop PV systems and demonstrating their daily feasibility were mentioned as key steps for the future.
- Lisbon — Lisbon found the tools useful for revisiting and potentially updating their existing monitoring systems, particularly in connection with the city's Climate Contract 2030.
- Milan — Milan may use the Guides in the future to identify funding opportunities that will allow for the further development of the methodologies tested within UP2030. The city will probably use the tool to identify funding that will enable the design and implementation of NBS that can effectively increase the ecosystem services provided by green spaces and urban resilience.
- Muenster — Muenster already has a climate action monitoring and financing system in place, including a climate budget. They noted that the existing financial climate controlling system within the city of Münster requires cooperation between several parties, so that an additional toolkit would be counterproductive in their case.
- Thessaloniki — Thessaloniki explored embedding the CBA Guide into city planning, especially to evaluate climate interventions like green roofs and energy retrofits. They can also benefit from the GF Guide, as it could support identifying suitable funding sources for these actions.

As of the time of writing of this report, Belfast, Rotterdam, and Zagreb had not uploaded the results of their discussions about the CBA and GF Guides into their Upscaling Phase reports. Any further comments and feedback provided by the end of the project will be considered, and the Guides will be updated by the end of 2025. For further information on the next steps, please see Section 5.

The developed Guides were designed to help municipalities to better plan and upscale their climate actions and to overcome their barriers to finance. In addition to the available Excel-based Guides, both

Guides will be integrated onto the UP2030 Service Platform in an online version. The purpose of the online tools is to improve the user experience and flow of use, by adding dynamic filters, help the users navigate across more modules and sections of the Guides in a more user-friendly way, and remove current obstacles such as the need to download the Guides and enable the Excel's macro functions. The Guides are planned to become available on the UP2030 Service Platform by the end of 2025. The UP2030 Service Platform is a knowledge hub designed to support cities and urban districts in their urban transformation, by offering tailored solutions, policy recommendations, methods and strategic tools developed by the UP2030 project (including the CBA and GF Guides). The Platform seeks to support city municipalities seeking innovative approaches to their urban planning processes and meet their climate and special justice goals. The Platform is under development, with a target publication date by the end of 2025. The current version of the platform is available via the following link: <https://urbanplanningfor2030.eu/>.

Downloadable Excel-based Guides may also be made available on the Platform, which is yet to be decided by the end of 2025.

The following sections provide an overview of key project components: Section 3 and Section 4 introduce the CBA and GF Guides, describing their purpose, structure, and main features; while Section 5 summarises the upcoming steps planned for advancing the project and further developing both Guides. Section 6 concludes the report.

3 CBA Guide

3.1 Status of the Guide

The CBA Guide's tool list, as of the time of reporting, includes 20 open-access CBA tools (introduced in more detail in Section 3.2.3). The structure of the CBA Guide and its functions are final and were made available to the UP2030 cities. Versions 1.1 and 1.2 were sent out by email to cities on 12 and 23 May 2025, while version 1.3 and 1.4, with 1.4 being the final version, were uploaded to the UP2030 internal SharePoint (that is accessible for all project partners, including municipality staff of pilot cities) (version 1.4. was uploaded on 22 July 2025). The working version of the Guide is in an Excel-based format, allowing users to access its functionalities and use the guide for its intended purpose. A preliminary web-based version of the CBA Guide is available at <https://urbanplanningfor2030.eu/form/cba-guide>, following the content, structure, and functionalities of the Excel-based version, and will be finalised together with ICLEI by the end of 2025.

3.2 Introducing the Guide

3.2.1 Purpose, structure and functionalities

The CBA Guide helps cities and users identify the most suitable open-source CBA tools, documents, and data sources to assess climate interventions. Through a simple questionnaire that captures project characteristics, sector focus, desired benefits, and available resources (like time and budget), it recommends a First- and Second-Best CBA tool tailored to the user's needs. It also filters out tools beyond their capacity, highlights data requirements, and provides links to relevant data sources, enabling users to prepare their own CBA effectively.

The CBA Guide's modules are made up of the "Intro", "Questionnaire", and "Tools Factsheets" worksheets, which are supported by internal and external Data Sources and the Annexes (see Figure 4).

- **Intro:** The Intro sheet gives an introduction to the CBA Guide.
- **Questionnaire:** This is the only sheet users need to interact with. By answering a short set of questions, such as sector, type of climate action, desired benefits, and available resources, users are guided to the most appropriate CBA tool for their needs. The Guide also suggests a Second-Best option in case the First-Best requires more resources than are available. It is important to note that no single CBA tool analyses all possible benefits. The list of benefits from which the user can choose depends on the selected climate action type and sector, which narrows down the number of available tools.
- **Tools Factsheets:** Provides background information on all CBA tools included in the Guide. Each tool's profile includes characteristics relevant to the questionnaire (e.g. data needs, sector focus, benefits covered). While all tools listed are open-access and free to use, the Guide also includes estimated resource requirements for each tool, referring to the amount of staff time and related human resource costs (e.g. working days or personnel input) typically needed for implementation.
- **Data sources:** A collection of data tables sourced from different tools.
- **Annexes:** Contain background material used to support the "Questionnaire" sheet. These sheets are not intended for user interaction but serve to ensure the Guide functions correctly.

Figure 4 shows the structure of the CBA Guide and the colour codes of the modules. The key modules have a dedicated colour (grey for the "Questionnaire" and blue for the "Tools Factsheets").

Figure 4: Structure of the Cost-Benefit Analysis Guide

The CBA tools included in this Guide have been selected based on their relevance, adaptability, and practicality for assessing urban sustainability and climate-related interventions in the UP2030 project context. All the included tools had to be publicly available and free to use, to ensure that they can be used by anyone and not to create a financial burden on the user. The methodology behind the selection prioritises tools that balance analytical accuracy (e.g. using correct formulas and models, accurately inputting and handling data) with user accessibility (e.g. free to use, has an included user manual), ensuring they can be used by local stakeholders with varying levels of technical expertise. The included tools have an Excel or web-based format where users can provide their own inputs. Research papers and other theoretical pieces that focus on the methodology of preparing a CBA calculation, without providing a practical interactive tool, were not included. Key criteria included the ability to capture both quantitative and qualitative impacts, compatibility with available data in urban settings, and being suitable for cities in Europe, therefore excluding tools that focus on cities in developing countries. The tools were also chosen for their ability to assess co-benefits, such as social and environmental outcomes, alongside economic costs and benefits. In terms of the climate focus, both climate change mitigation and adaptation-focused tools were included, with some of them focusing solely on one or the other, while others include both aspects of the urban climate action. In addition, the selection of tools provides a good balance between city and project-level tools.

Following the selection of the tools based on the criteria described above, 20 open-access tools were incorporated, which users can use to prepare their own CBA calculation. When users fill out the "Questionnaire", they can see their First-Best and Second-Best tool to use, with their related descriptions, that contain a general overview of the tool and other relevant information such as their climate focus, level, degree of detail, sectoral coverage, benefits, a summary of data requirements and their estimated resource requirements in the number of working days (internal use) and estimated cost in Euros (external use). All the included CBA tools are open-access and free to use. The costs included in the estimated resource section refer to the estimated cost of outsourcing the analysis to a third-party (e.g. external consultant), in case such an exercise would not be carried out internally by the user.

As Table 2 shows (next page), the included tools cover sectors such as transport, buildings, waste, urban parks, agriculture, industry, and energy. Out of the 20 tools, 3 have a climate change adaptation focus, 13 focus on climate change mitigation, and the remaining 4 consider both objectives. 9 of the included tools can calculate costs and benefits at a project level, whilst 10 of them carry out these calculations at the city level. Only 1 tool has the option to make a CBA calculation at both the city and project levels.

Table 2: Tools included in the CBA Guide

Level	Tool name	Climate focus	Sectoral focus						
			Transport	Buildings	Waste	Urban parks	Agriculture	Industry	Energy
Project level	CRC: Climate Resilient City Tool	Adaptation		X		X			
	EDGE: Excellence in Design for Greater Efficiencies	Mitigation		X					
	C40 Equitable Impacts toolbox: Bus Rapid Transit Systems	Mitigation	X						
	C40 Equitable Impacts toolbox: Congestion Pricing	Mitigation	X						
	C40 Equitable Impacts toolbox: Cool Roofs	Mitigation		X					
	C40 Equitable Impacts toolbox: Waste Collection & Segregation	Mitigation			X				
	C40 Heat Resilient Cities Tool	Adaptation		X		X			
	MICAT: Multiple Impact Calculation Tool	Mitigation	X	X			X	X	
	NATURE Tool	Adaptation		X		X	X		
Both	SAVi: Sustainable Asset Valuation	Both	X	X	X		X	X	X
City level	AQUA: Air Quality through Urban Actions	Mitigation	X	X			X	X	
	Carbon and Co-benefits Decision Support Tool	Both	X	X					X
	Climate Opportunity Interactive Dashboard	Mitigation	X	X					X
	CURB: Climate Action for Urban Sustainability	Both	X	X	X				X
	C40 Healthy Neighbourhoods Explorer	Both	X	X		X			
	HEAT: Health economic assessment tool	Mitigation	X						
	HERB: C40 Healthy and Efficient Retrofitted Buildings Tool	Mitigation		X					
	C40 Pathways Air Quality (AQ)	Mitigation		X	X			X	X
	TRACE: Co-Benefits Evaluation Tool for the Urban Transport Sector	Mitigation	X						
	Net Zero City Planner	Mitigation	X	X	X				X

3.2.2 Questionnaire

The "Questionnaire" module consists of a questionnaire, the results that are provided by the algorithm based on the answers that they provided (results consist of links to the missing data sources and the First- and Second-Best Tools), and a section where users can see their First- and Second-Best Tools' dedicated factsheets.

The questionnaire is a simple form that users (i.e. "you" in the questionnaire) need to fill in, divided into three parts: 1) needs assessment, 2) information on data availability and 3) resource availability. First, as part of the needs assessment, users need to answer the following questions:

- **What do you want to do?** — Users can select if they just want to get more familiar with the topic of CBA, if they are interested in a light approach to CBA and want to have a rough overview of the costs and benefits of their project, or if they want a detailed CBA. A detailed CBA yields more sophisticated results but also requires more resources than a light approach.
- **Are you interested in mitigation or adaptation projects?** — Users need to select if they want to see tools that focus on climate change mitigation, adaptation, or both. Choosing the option of mitigation and adaptation leads to tools that cover both aspects but limits the number of suitable tools because not all tools can address both.
- **Which sector would you like to focus on in your activity?** — Users can select the following sectors: transport, buildings, waste management, urban parks, agriculture, industry, and energy. The choice of sector is high-level and may contain subsectors (e.g. renewable energy and energy efficiency as subsectors of energy); only one sector can be selected per query to ensure accurate selection of tools.
- **What benefits would you like to include in the CBA?** — Users can select benefits in four categories: health, environment, cost savings as well as economic and social. Selecting many benefits may lead to a more comprehensive CBA, but it narrows down the number of suitable CBA tools such that the First-Best Tool might be less useful than if fewer benefits are selected. No benefit might show up in a category if there are no available tools to consider the specific benefit based on the given answers to the question above.

Second, users need to answer the following question, focusing on data availability:

- **What type of national or local data do you have available?** — Users need to specify the available data. The data needs to change based on the previously selected answers, and only the relevant data needs to show up. Local or national data is usually more accurate than international sources, so users are advised to use local data if available. If local data is not available, the Guide provides links to data sources that can help fill the data gaps.

Third, they need to provide information on the available resources to carry out their CBA by answering:

- **What resources are you going to use for the activity?** — Users need to specify if they are going to use internal or external resources for carrying out the CBA.
- **What is the amount of your resources available for the activity?** — Depending on the previous answer, i.e. if the CBA is carried out internally or externally, the users need to select the number of days available, if the analysis is carried out internally, or the amount in Euros, if it is outsourced (e.g. to an external consultant).

As Figure 5 shows, Output 1 and 2 are the First- and Second-Best Tools that the algorithm provides based on the provided answers, while Output 3 is the suggestion for the data sources, based on the identified data gaps in the question targeting data availability. Figure 6 shows an example of a filled-out questionnaire.

Figure 5: Structure of the CBA Guide's questionnaire

Question	Answers										
What do you want to do?	Light approach to CBA for a rough overview of costs and benefits of my project										
Are you interested in mitigation or adaptation projects?	Mitigation										
Which sector would you like to focus on in your activity?	Transport										
What benefits would you like to include in the CBA?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Health <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Environment <input type="checkbox"/> Cost savings <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Economic and social Physical health Air pollution Road Asset value of buildings										
What type of national or local data do you have available?	Transport activity data: Yes Vehicle data (occupancy, load factors, kilometers, fuel): No Road kilometers and travel speed: No Number of fatalities in transport: No										
What resources are you going to use for the activity?	Internal resources by dedicating staff time										
What is the amount of your resources available for the activity?	4-10 days										
First-best tool	Trace TRACE - Co-benefits in decarbonising transport , NewClimate Institute										
Second-best tool	Health Economic Assessment Tool (HEAT) HEAT v5.2.0 , heatwalkingcycling.org										
Links to data sources to address indicated data gaps	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Data source</th> <th>Data source type</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Vehicle data (occupancy, load factors, kilometers, fuel consumption)</td> <td>Vehicle Occupancy Load Factor Vehicle fuel efficiency Data provided within the tool</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Road kilometers and travel speed</td> <td>No global dataset available; the tool may provide default data</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Number of fatalities in transport</td> <td>https://www.who.int/data/gho/data/indicators/indicator-details/GHO/estimated-number-of-road-traffic-deaths External source</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Data and Trends - Mobility Division (tamu.edu) External source</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Data source	Data source type	Vehicle data (occupancy, load factors, kilometers, fuel consumption)	Vehicle Occupancy Load Factor Vehicle fuel efficiency Data provided within the tool	Road kilometers and travel speed	No global dataset available; the tool may provide default data	Number of fatalities in transport	https://www.who.int/data/gho/data/indicators/indicator-details/GHO/estimated-number-of-road-traffic-deaths External source		Data and Trends - Mobility Division (tamu.edu) External source
Data source	Data source type										
Vehicle data (occupancy, load factors, kilometers, fuel consumption)	Vehicle Occupancy Load Factor Vehicle fuel efficiency Data provided within the tool										
Road kilometers and travel speed	No global dataset available; the tool may provide default data										
Number of fatalities in transport	https://www.who.int/data/gho/data/indicators/indicator-details/GHO/estimated-number-of-road-traffic-deaths External source										
	Data and Trends - Mobility Division (tamu.edu) External source										

Figure 6: Example of the filled-out Questionnaire module⁴

⁴ The screenshots showing the Excel-based Guides have illustration purposes only. All the important information regarding their content and structure are summarised in the text.

Once the questionnaire is filled out and the user clicks on the "Show links to tools" button, the First- and Second-Best Tools, and relevant data sources appear below the questionnaire. The First-Best Tool is the closest to the user's needs without taking into account resource constraints, while the Second-Best Tool considers the available resources. Figure 7 shows an example of how the First- and Second-Best Tools and their related factsheets are displayed when the questionnaire is filled out with the inputs shown in Figure 6.

A	B	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M
31		Trace				Health Economic Assessment Tool (HEAT)			
32	Link to tool	TRACE - Co-benefits in decarbonising transport				HEAT v5.2.0			
	Description	TRACE is an Excel-based tool that quantifies key non-climate impacts of urban transport decarbonization, such as reduced congestion, accidents, and fuel use. Results are given in physical and monetary terms, requiring external transport scenarios as inputs. TRACE requires external urban transport scenarios as inputs but does not generate them.				HEAT is a tool designed to assess the economic health impacts of walking and cycling, even for users without expertise in impact evaluation. It calculates the value of reduced mortality from physical activity, accounting for factors like air pollution and traffic accidents. HEAT is useful for transport planners and local professionals to evaluate current levels, compare scenarios, and assess the benefits of new projects.			
33									
34	Focus	Mitigation				Mitigation			
35	Level	City level				City level			
36	Degree of detail	Medium				Medium			
	Sector coverage	Transport				Transport			
37									
	Benefits	Congestion, Road, Fuel saving, Air pollution				GHG emissions, Air pollution, Crash risk, Number of lives saved, Value of statistical life, Social cost of carbon			
38									
	Data requirements (summary)	Transport activity data, Vehicle data (occupancy, load factors, kilometers, fuel consumption), Road kilometers and travel speed, Number of fatalities in transport, -				Population data (size), Transport-related data (travel time per capita and transport mode), Health data (mortality rate per transport mode, road fatalities), Value of statistical life			
39									
40	Estimated resource requirements	4 working days or USD 5000				2 working days or USD 2000			
41	Related guides	-	-	-	-	C40 Cities (2020), C40 MER Ir Link			
42		-	-	-	-	C40 Cities (2021), Benefits of Link			
43		-	-	-	-	CIVITAS (2020), CIVITAS 2020 Link			
44		-	-	-	-	IGES (2011), The Transport C Link			
45		-	-	-	-	KfW Development Bank (2011) Link			

Figure 7: Example of the questionnaire's result

3.2.3 Tools factsheets

While the filled-out "Questionnaire" provides the user with a First- and Second-Best Tool and their dedicated factsheets under the filled-out questionnaire, they cannot see every tool included in the CBA Guide. Therefore, the CBA Guide has a dedicated worksheet, the "Tools factsheets", where users can browse across the 20 included CBA tools and see all the relevant information in one place. As Figure 8 shows, users can find here information about the tool, such as their links, a short description, their climate focus, degree of detail, level, sectoral coverage, benefits, and the data and resource requirements. In addition, the factsheets also provide links to relevant guides, which either explicitly mention the tool or similar benefits/objectives are mentioned, and case studies that provide real-life examples of how the mentioned tool was used. Relevant user guides were also added to help users inform themselves about the steps of using the tool and preparing their own CBA calculation.

	A	B	C
1	CBA TOOLS	Trace	C40 Heat Resilient Cities
2	Link	TRACE - Co-benefits in decarbonising transport NewClimate Institute	Heat Resilient Cities: Measuring benefits of urban heat adaptation (c40knowledgehub.org)
3	Description	TRACE is an Excel-based tool that quantifies key non-climate impacts of urban transport decarbonization, such as reduced congestion, accidents, and fuel use. Results are given in physical and monetary terms, requiring external transport scenarios as inputs. TRACE requires external urban transport scenarios as inputs but does not generate them.	The Heat Resilient Cities tool quantifies the health benefits of urban heat adaptation actions, helping city planners and decision-makers assess and prioritize interventions. It provides evidence for investing in heat mitigation and identifies the most effective strategies. Developed through extensive research, the tool is based on action-to-impact analysis and expert reviews.
4	Focus	Mitigation	Adaptation
5	Degree of detail	Medium	Medium
6	Level	City level	Project level
7	Sector coverage	- Transport	- Urban parks - Urban water - Cool artificial surfaces - Cool vegetation surfaces - Heat action plans, for information purpose only

Figure 8: Screenshot of the "Tools factsheets" module

3.3 Using the Guide

This section explains the use of the Excel-based Guide. The online version on the UP2030 Service Platform will follow the same logic and functionality.

Key steps of using the CBA Guide:

1. **Intro sheet:** Get familiarised with the Guide by reading the introduction for context on UP2030, the purpose of the Guide, and instructions on navigating it.
2. **Shortlisting the available CBA tools and data sources:** go to the "Questionnaire" module and fill out the following:
 - Select the level of detail of your preferred CBA approach. A detailed CBA yields more sophisticated results but also requires more resources than a light approach.
 - Choose the climate change mitigation and/or adaptation focus. Choosing the option of both leads to tools that cover both aspects but limits the number of suitable tools.
 - Select the sectoral focus. The choice of sector is high-level and may contain subsectors (e.g. renewable energy and energy efficiency as subsectors of energy).
 - Select the benefits that the city would like to include in the CBA.
 - Choose what type of national or local data is available.
 - Select what resources the city is going to use for the activity.
3. **Click on "Show links to tools" and review your results:** The First-Best Tool is the tool that best fits your needs according to the selected options. The Second-Best Tool takes additionally considers your resource constraints. If the First- and Second-Best Tools are different, it means that you would need more resources to be able to apply the First-Best Tool. Users can see the factsheets of the First- and Second-Best Tools that contain key information such as their links, a short description, their climate focus, degree of detail, level, sectoral coverage, benefits, and the data and resource requirements. In addition, the factsheets also provide links to relevant guides, case studies and user manuals for the tools.

4. **Browse the "Tools factsheets" module:** For reviewing all the tools included in the CBA Guide and their related information, including case studies, go to the "Tools factsheets" module.

Tips:

- The column on the right of the questionnaire offers guiding comments to help users understand how their answers affect the filtering process. These tips explain trade-offs, constraints, and why some tools may or may not appear.
- To reset and restart the process, click the "Clear all cells" button.

3.4 Limitations of the CBA Guide

One of the main limitations of the CBA Guide is the lack of available tools focusing on climate change adaptation (only three such tools are available). This results from the lack of available tools that can monetise the costs and benefits of adaptation measures, and the lack of consistent assessment methods. While it is not the objective of this Guide, it is important to note that the Guide cannot do the CBA calculation. It is the responsibility of the users to access and use the First- and Second-Best Tools recommended by the Guide as per the filled-in questionnaire.

Furthermore, a successful CBA analysis is subject to high-quality, granular data. The CBA Guide provides internal data sources for trip distance, vehicle fuel efficiency, vehicle load factors, trips' modal shares, proportion of wastewater by treatment method and wastewater generation factors, solid waste generation, and value of statistical life (VSL), and also a number of external data sources to cover the remaining data requirements. However, in most cases, these are global datasets with national averages, which might result in inaccurate results when they are used to calculate CBA at a city or project level. Therefore, users are advised to use their own data, subject to availability, to ensure that the used data has the highest resolution and granularity and improve the results of their analysis.

The Questionnaire of the CBA Guide is based on the Excel's macro function (i.e. automated requests collect the needed information from the Excel's locked worksheets and display it in the Questionnaire's tool factsheet section in a comprehensive way), which is only available in the Excel's desktop version. Therefore, users are advised to download and open an offline version of the CBA Guide, instead of opening it in their browsers. When opening the Excel, a pop-up message requests the user to enable macros. Users are required to enable the macros to allow the Guide's functionalities to work. The web-based version of the tool, which is currently under development, will solve this problem and will provide a smoother user experience.

4 Green Finance Guide

4.1 Status of the Guide

The Excel-based GF Guide, in terms of structure, content and functionalities, are final. GF Guide lists 102 financing instruments, 73 case studies, 8 key blending strategies, 44 financing and TA programmes and 12 key stakeholders providing finance (12). The structure of the CBA Guide and its functions are final and were made available to UP2030 cities. Versions 1.1 and 1.2 were sent out by email to cities on 12 and 23 May 2025, while versions 1.3-1.5, with 1.5 being the final version, were uploaded to the internal UP2030 SharePoint (version 1.5 was uploaded on 30 July 2025).

Web-based version of the GF Guide is yet to be developed on the UP2030 Service Platform by the end of 2025. As a result, some functionalities may differ from the Excel-based version. The current online version is available on the Platform via: <https://urbanplanningfor2030.eu/form/green-finance-guide>.

The final content of the Excel-based GF Guide is described in the following sections, including its structure and functionalities in 4.2.1, and its key modules in the following sections.

4.2 Introducing the Guide

4.2.1 Purpose, structure and functionalities

The purpose of the GF Guide is to provide a comprehensive overview of financial instruments and mechanisms available for municipalities to finance their climate action. Its purpose is to inform municipalities about a wide range of financial instruments and to offer high-level guidance on how to combine or blend these instruments to unlock and secure investment, highlighting key stakeholders involved in the provision of finance. It also showcases real-world case studies that demonstrate how financial instruments and mechanisms were applied for urban climate action. It also includes a curated list of financing and TA programmes that are accessible to municipalities across Europe.

The Guide is structured into separate thematic modules (see Figure 9). The three core modules: "Financial Instruments", "Case Studies", and "International Financing and Technical Assistance Programmes" are searchable databases that allow users to filter, identify, and explore options relevant to their context. Complementary modules provide high-level guidance and explanatory support, helping users understand how to navigate the broader climate finance landscape, structure financing approaches, and engage with stakeholders. Together, these modules aim to either support early-stage project planning or upscaling by helping cities identify appropriate financing strategies, key stakeholders and programmes and draw insights from real-world examples.

The GF Guide's main modules are the "Inputs" module, developed to shortlist tailored solutions for the Searchable modules ("Financial Instruments", "Case Studies", "International Financing and Technical Assistance Programmes") supported by the complementary support modules, along with the Intro and Glossary worksheets (see Figure 9).

- **Intro:** Gives an introduction to the GF Guide, including purpose, high-level user guide and disclaimer.
- **Inputs:** Serves as the starting module for shortlisting results in key searchable databases. It hosts a list of filters that allows users to shortlist results in the key modules: "Financial Instruments", "Case Studies", and "International Financing and Technical Assistance Programmes". This sheet acts as the central entry point for navigating the Guide's content through embedded links and filter options. The operability of the "Input" sheet uses Excel's macro function (i.e. automated commands to set the right filters), which is only available in the Excel's desktop version. Therefore, users must download and open an offline version of the GF Guide, instead of opening it in their browsers, to be able to use the Guide as intended.

When opening the Excel, a pop-up message requests the user to enable macros, hence allowing the Guide's functionalities to work.

- **Financial Instruments:** A searchable database listing conventional and innovative financial instruments and mechanisms. All instruments are categorised for a tailored search.
- **Case Studies:** Provides categorised case examples of how financial instruments and mechanisms have been applied in urban climate projects.
- **International Financing and Technical Assistance Programmes:** Offers a list of key international funders, financing and TA programmes available to European municipalities.
- **Key Stakeholders:** High-level overview of key types of stakeholders providing finance for municipalities, including definitions, relevant financial instruments, examples of real-world stakeholders and relevant case studies.
- **Blending:** Explains how different financial instruments and mechanisms can be strategically combined to support complex funding needs.
- **Readiness and Risk Assessment:** An optional self-assessment tool that allows users to evaluate their project's risk and investment readiness to search for instruments according to their risk appetite.
- **Glossary:** Provides clear definitions of key terms used throughout the Guide to support user understanding.

Figure 9 shows the structure of the GF Guide and the colour codes of the modules. The key modules have a dedicated colour (e.g. purple for "Financial Instruments", blue for "Case Studies, etc.). These colour codes are used across the Guide's modules. For example, the header of the column for showcasing case studies in the "Financial Instruments" module is marked with the same blue colour as the "Case Study" module.

Figure 9: Structure of the Green Finance Guide

The Guide categorises entries for filtering, which enables users to tailor the output according to their specific needs. This list of filters allows users to shortlist results in the key modules: "Financial Instruments", "Case Studies", and "International Financing and Technical Assistance Programmes".

All modules in the GF Guide are interlinked via hyperlinks, making it easier to navigate between the related content. Hyperlinks lead users to the related datapoints or whole modules to find out more information. As it can happen that, for example, some instruments included in the case studies on the "Case Studies" module are filtered out from the "Financing Instruments" module because of the filter selection set in the "Input" module. To solve this, and allow the user to access all the information, when clicking on a hyperlink leading to a cell within the document, filters will be reset, and the pop-up message shown in Figure 10 will show up. If the user wants to see the initial filtering, they will need to go back to the "Inputs" module and click the "Filter results" button.

Figure 10: Pop-up window after the filters are cleared in the Green Finance Guide

As Figure 11 shows, the three main modules share some key functions and filterable content (categorisations), while the support modules provide additional functions to them. For example, the "Financial Instruments" module contains information on which stakeholder is most relevant, providing that particular type of finance, which is linked to the "Key Stakeholders" module to provide more information on the type of stakeholders. Similarly, the relevant financing instruments are listed on the "Key Stakeholders" module. Another example is that the "Case Study" module is linked to the "Financial Instruments" module, as they are showcased as examples for the relevant instruments, while the case studies in the "Case Study" module list the specific instruments that were used and are hyperlinked to the related instrument on the "Financial Instruments" module. At the same time, all modules can be used independently of each other, thus providing information that can be used on their own, according to the specific needs of the users.

Figure 11: Linkages between the modules of the Green Finance Guide

4.2.2 Inputs

The Guide's "Input" sheet (see Figure 12) acts as the central entry point for navigating the Guide's content through embedded links and filter options (due to categorisation of instruments, case studies and financing and TA programmes in individual modules). On the "Input" sheet, the filters are organised into two main sections:

1. Investment Project Characterisation

This section allows users to define the general profile of the investment project using dropdown lists. Available categories include:

- **Sector:** Filters the targeted economic sector, reflect areas where instruments have been applied or have the potential to be applied.
- **Climate action type:** Climate change mitigation, adaptation, or both.

These selections help refine the information displayed in the main modules.

2. Module-Specific Filters

Additional filters are provided in the form of check-boxes, enabling more granular selection within different modules:

- **Financial Instruments:** Instrument type, modality, source of finance, category of blending, instrument maturity, and investment readiness and risk.
- **Case Studies:** Region, city size, investment size, and type of case study.

- **International Financing and Technical Assistance Programmes:** Type of assistance and eligibility for EU Member States.

Users must make at least one selection in each category to generate results. To facilitate the filtering process, the tool includes convenient "Select all filters" and "Clear all filters" buttons at the bottom of the filter list, allowing users to quickly apply or reset their selections. This approach ensures that users can efficiently navigate the dataset and obtain outputs that are closely aligned with their specific interests and requirements.

3	Investment project characterization	
4		
5	Sector	All sectors
6		
7	Climate action type	Climate change mitigation and adaptation
8		
9	Financial Instruments	
10		
11	Instrument type	Debt <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
12		Equity <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
13		Public <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
14		Grant <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
15		Risk transfer or mitigation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
16		Market based <input type="checkbox"/>
17		
18	Modality	Repayable <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
19		Non-repayable <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
20		De-risking <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
21		Results-based <input type="checkbox"/>
22		
23	Source of finance	Public (Domestic) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
24		Public (International) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
25		Public (Municipal own source revenue) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
26		Private <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
27		Mixed (public and private) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
28		
29	Category of blending	Structured funds and facilities <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
30		Insurance <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
31		Grants <input type="checkbox"/>
32		Loans and debt financing <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
33		Instruments <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
34		Guarantees <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
35		Outcome funding/ Results-based financing <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
36	Equity financing <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
37	Not blending instrument <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
38		
39	Instrument maturity	Mature <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
40		Emerging <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
41		Pilot <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
42		
43	Investment readiness and risk	Low risk, high readiness <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
44		Medium risk and readiness <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
45		High risk, low readiness <input type="checkbox"/>
46	Case studies	
47		
48	Region	North America <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
49		South America <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
50		Europe <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
51		Africa <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
52		Asia <input type="checkbox"/>
53		Australia and Oceania <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
54		
55	City size	Multiple cities <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
56		Mega (population >2M) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
57		Large (population 0.5M-2M) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
58		Medium (population 0.2M-0.5M) <input type="checkbox"/>
59		Small (population <0.2M) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
60		
61	Investment size	Large (>300M EUR) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
62		Medium (50-300M EUR) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
63		Small (<50M EUR) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
64		
65	Type of case study	Blending instruments <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
66		Innovative financial instruments <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
67		Private finance <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
68		
69	International Financing and Technical Assistance Programmes	
70		
71	Type of assistance	Finance provision <input type="checkbox"/>
72		Capacity building & technical assistance <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
73		
74	Eligibility for EU Member States	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
75		No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
76		Selected <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
77		
78		Select all filters
79		Clear all filters
80		
81		
82		Filter results
83		

Figure 12: Screenshot of the "Inputs" module

In addition to using the filter options on the "Input" sheet, users can also use filters directly on the "Financial Instruments", "Case Studies" and "International Financing and Technical Assistance Programmes" modules. Within these modules, descriptive content is shown in grey-shaded header rows, while filterable fields are marked in yellow cells (see Figure 13). Users can filter the content based on their interests by using the yellow, filterable headers and selecting the relevant options from the dropdown lists.

CASE STUDIES		Filters	Filters
Descriptive content		Descriptive content	Descriptive content
#	Name of case study	Region	Country
1	Residential energy efficiency instruments in Lithuania	Europe	Lithuania

City size	Project investment size	Climate action type	Sector(s)
Mega (population >2M), Large (population 0.5M-2M), Medium (population 0.2M-0.5M), Small (population <0.2M)	Large (>300M EUR), Medium (50-300M EUR), Small (<50M EUR)	Climate change mitigation, Climate change adaptation, Climate change mitigation and adaptation	Transportation and mobility, Buildings and energy efficiency, Energy generation and systems, Water, waste and wastewater, Urban development and management, Green spaces and nature-based solutions, Disaster risk management
Multiple cities	Medium (50-300M EUR)	Climate change mitigation	X

Figure 13: Filters and descriptive panels

4.2.3 Financial Instruments

The "Financial Instruments" module (see Figure 14) is a searchable database of conventional and innovative financial instruments and mechanisms. Instruments are not only grouped by theme (e.g. grants, thematic bonds, guarantees) but also categorised according to several filterable characteristics. Users can apply filters in the "Inputs" sheet or directly in the sheet header to shortlist instruments relevant to their project needs. Each entry includes descriptive information (e.g. description, benefits, challenges, EU taxonomy) as well as the types of stakeholders providing finance and examples of real-world applications. Hyperlinks connect each instrument to real-world case studies, blending strategies and stakeholder information across other modules.

#	Category	Instruments and mechanisms	Description	Benefits
3	Municipal revenue (Own-source revenues, OSRs)	Tax abatements for positive action	Tax incentives targeting developers for low-carbon and resilient projects	A flexible tool to encourage private sector and residents to invest in energy-efficient, low-carbon measures
4		Tax or rebates on negative development aspects	Cities are imposing taxes on features not aligned with low-carbon development and offering rebates from transportation or industrial polluters.	Tax schemes can generate extra revenue, ideally encouraging compliance with low-carbon and resilient goals.
5		Tax-line financing for clean energy and energy efficiency measures	Tax-line financing mechanisms that allow a commercial or private property owner to finance the up-front cost of energy, water or other eligible improvements on a property and then pay the costs back over time via tax or service charges.	This method reduces upfront costs for energy efficiency measures, helping residents and businesses to reduce their energy costs and environmental impact via affordable loans that can be paid off in instalments.
			Pricing or charging fees for behaviors harming air	Charging and pricing can create significant

Figure 14: Screenshot of the "Financial instruments" module

The structure of the module and the categorisation of the covered information were based on the climate finance landscape can be described along several dimensions:

Source of finance:

- By domain: whether it is public, private, or a mix of both.
- By origin: whether it is raised domestically, within a country's own borders, or internationally, either bilaterally (from one country to another) or multilaterally (from multiple countries to another). It can come from national or subnational governments, international organisations (including development banks), corporations, multilateral funds, or various financial institutions.

Type of finance:

- The instrument or mechanism used, such as public, equity, or debt.

Maturity of finance:

- The maturity of the instruments, whether it is mature, emerging, or pilot.

Modality of finance:

- The category for the instruments' modality covers repayable instruments (e.g. green investment funds, green loans and municipal bonds) and non-repayable (e.g. traditional grants, taxes, or rebates on negative development aspects, development charges). In addition, the Guide includes de-risking (e.g. risk insurance products) and result-based instruments (e.g. Energy Performance Contracts (EPC)) as well. Similarly, financial instruments are categorised based on the source of the finance.

Sector and objective:

- The economic sector targeted and whether the financing supports climate mitigation, adaptation, or disaster recovery.

For further information on the definition of the categories used in the module, see the Glossary.

Cities have a range of mechanisms and instruments available to access funding. They can rely on their OSR, which include local taxes and fees paid by residents, or turn to external sources. These external funds may come in the form of loans, grants, or through mobilising private sector investment (see Figure 15).

Figure 15: The financing landscape blueprint for listing and categorising financing instruments in the GF Guide

4.2.4 Case Studies

The "Case Studies" module (see Figure 16) provides categorised, and thus filterable, case examples of different financial instruments and mechanisms that have been applied in urban climate projects. Each case study includes information on the financing structure used and is cross-referenced with the relevant instruments in the "Financial Instruments" module. Hyperlinks connect to related instruments and stakeholders to provide context and guidance. The case studies were collected from open-source case study collections, and the users can find additional information when clicking on the provided links.

	A	B	C	D	E	I	J	K
1	CASE STUDIES							
2								
3			Location		City size	Project investment size	Climate action type	
4	#	Name of case study	Region	Country	City	Multiple cities, Mega (population >2M), Large (population 0.5M-2M), Medium (population 0.2M-0.5M), Small (population <0.2M)	Large (>300M EUR), Medium (50-300M EUR), Small (<50M EUR)	Climate change mitigation, Climate change adaptation, Climate change mitigation and adaptation
5	1	Residential energy efficiency instruments in Lithuania	Europe	Lithuania	Multiple	Multiple cities	Medium (50-300M EUR)	Climate change mitigation
	2	Cape Town Green Bond	Africa	South Africa	Capetown	Mega (population >2M)	Medium (50-300M EUR)	Climate change mitigation and adaptation

Figure 16: Screenshot of the "Case Studies" module

The module includes 73 case studies that cover all global geographic regions (Africa, Asia, Australia and Oceania, Europe, North America, and South America), more than 47 cities, and illustrate the use of 82 different types of financing instruments that are included in the "Financial Instruments" module. Users can filter the most relevant case studies by selecting the investment size and city size based on their population. As Figure 17 shows, case studies cover 7 sectors with the water, waste, and wastewater (21) and the buildings and energy efficiency (18) sectors providing the most examples. In terms of climate action type, there are 30 case studies covering climate change adaptation, 33 covering climate change mitigation and 10 of them covering both. Users can additionally narrow their search by selecting the case study type, which can provide information on the innovative nature of the case studies (1), whether different financing instruments were blended (2) and if private finance was used (3). In sum, case studies can be filtered according to sector, climate action type, region, city size, investment size and type of case study. Figure 17 provides an overview of case studies, showing filterable information in yellow.

Figure 17: Case studies in the Green Finance Guide

4.2.5 International Financing and Technical Assistance Programmes

The "International Financing and Technical Assistance Programmes" module (see Figure 18) offers a searchable list of key international funds, financing, and TA programmes available to European municipalities. Users can filter by eligibility, type of assistance (e.g. finance provision, technical support), climate objective and sectoral focus. Each programme includes links to additional details and lists key instruments provided.

INTERNATIONAL FINANCING & TECHNICAL ASSISTANCE PROGRAMMES								
#	Category	Stakeholder	Name of programme	Eligibility (geographical)	Eligibility for EU Member States		Type of assistance	
					Yes, No, Selected	Finance provision	Capacity building & technical assistance	
1		European Investment Bank	European Local Energy Assistance (ELENA)	EU Member States	Yes			X
2		European Investment Bank	Municipal Framework Loans	EU Member States	Yes	X		X
3		European Investment Bank	Municipal Project Support	Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus,	No			X

Figure 18: Screenshot of the "International Financing and Technical Assistance Programmes" module

4.2.6 Key Stakeholders

The "Key Stakeholders" is a complementary module to the searchable databases (modules) (see Figure 19). It lists key types of stakeholders providing green finance for municipalities and includes definitions, relevant financial instruments, examples of real-world stakeholders and relevant case studies. Users can find relevant stakeholders listed in each financial instrument and case studies, which are hyperlinked to the stakeholder entries in this module, allowing them to trace and understand key stakeholders providing finance and their institutional roles.

KEY STAKEHOLDERS PROVIDING FINANCE		
Key stakeholders	Definition	Examples of financial instruments
Local/subnational government	With direct responsibility for essential services and infrastructure, local and regional governments are uniquely positioned to plan, finance, and deliver projects that build resilience and advance sustainability goals. To fund local resilience and sustainability initiatives, municipalities can leverage municipal budgets, issue green bonds, establish public-private partnerships, access national and international climate funds, and introduce local taxes or fees for sustainability initiatives. The ability to access and deploy different financial instruments, often depends on the broader enabling environment, such as the degree of fiscal and financial autonomy (e.g., the ability to introduce new taxes) and national regulatory frameworks (e.g., limitation on municipality debt levels).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Municipal budget spending - Land banking and land readjustment - City climate and green funds - Regional development funds - Revolving funds (revolving credit facilities) - Contingency and reserve funds - Traditional grants - Recoverable grants - Performance-based grants - Capital grants - Energy Performance Contracts (EPC) - Internal contracting - Pooled procurement - Aggregation platforms - Microcredit - Microleasing

Figure 19: Screenshot of the "Key stakeholders" module

4.2.7 Blending

The "Blending" module (see Figure 20) serves as an informative, complementary module to the searchable databases. It provides an overview of how different financial instruments and mechanisms can be strategically combined to support complex funding needs. The "Blending" module's categories are aligned with the "Financial Instruments" module and include descriptions, value propositions, and real-world examples. Hyperlinks can connect the users to relevant instruments and case studies to illustrate how blending is applied in practice.

A	B	C	D	E
1	BLENDING STRATEGIES			
2				
3	Category of blending <i>Structured funds and facilities, Insurance, Grants, Loans and debt financing</i> # <i>Instruments, Guarantees, Outcome funding/ Results-based financing, Equity financing, Not blending instrument</i>	Key financial instruments and mechanisms	Value proposition of blending	How is it provided
4				
5	1 Structured funds and facilities	Structured Funds and Facilities: - Debt Funds - Climate & Green Funds - Multi-Donor Trust Funds - Blended Finance Funds - Revolving Credit Facilities - Regional Development Facilities - Outcome-Based Facilities - Liquidity Facilities - Sector-Specific Facilities - Risk-Sharing Facilities - Public-Private Partnership (PPP) Facilities - Impact Investment Facilities - Guarantee Facilities - Pooled Grant Facilities	Structured funds offer different asset classes and cater to the development objectives of public donors and Development Financial Institutions (DFIs) and the investment objectives of private investors. Private investors benefit from the waterfall structure's reduced risk, enabling them to invest in sectors and regions with high development potential and higher perceived risk. Publicly funded donor agencies benefit from revolving or continuously using their funds for sustainable development. Further, structured funds pool money from various sources to invest in many different countries and sometimes sectors, enabling risk diversification and reducing the risk of losses.	The combination of concessional funding (public or philanthropic funds) with full return private capital or investments in companies regular equity or bonds.

Figure 20: Screenshot of the "Blending" module

4.2.8 Readiness and Risk Assessment

The "Readiness and Risk Assessment" module (see Figure 21) allows users to self-evaluate their project's maturity and risk level. By completing a short, high-level questionnaire, users receive a risk score (1–3) with a corresponding risk and readiness category, which can then be used to filter instruments by risk level on the "Inputs" sheet or directly in the "Financial Instruments" module. This module is optional; users may filter by any selected readiness and risk category in the "Financial Instruments" module, without having to fill out the readiness and risk assessment scoring.

	A	B	C	D	E	F
1	PROJECT READINESS AND RISK ASSEMENT SCORING GUIDE					
2			Self-assessment by cities (To be filled by users)	Guide for self-assessment		
3	Criteria		[Low risk, high readiness = 1 point; Medium risk and readiness = 2 points; High risk, low readiness = 3 points]	Low risk, high readiness = 1 point	Medium risk and readiness = 2 points	High risk, low readiness = 3 points
4	A. Project readiness	Degree of bankability		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High probability of meeting the project's financial, environmental, and social goals Sufficient estimated cash flows to cover costs and produce returns that meet investor expectations Project is implemented by a creditworthy entity Financing the scale-up of a tested solution or technology 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Moderate probability of meeting financial, environmental, and social goals Reasonable but uncertain cash flows, capable of covering costs Implemented by an entity with moderate creditworthiness, possibly needing additional guarantees 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Low probability, and high uncertainty of meeting financial, environmental, and social goals Insufficient or highly uncertain cash flows, unable to cover costs reliably Implemented by an entity with low creditworthiness, lacking necessary guarantees Most likely a pilot project
5	A. Project readiness	Project readiness (development phase, technology readiness (TRL) level)		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> There is a governance structure in place Legal contracts have been established Investors have been identified and contact High municipality capacity to undertake administrative tasks of financing a project TRL 7-9, equal to maturity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> There is a Business Case and Financial Model available for the projects There is a Baseline and Estimate for the project impacts supported by feasibility studies Main stakeholders are identified and engaged with Low municipality capacity to undertake administrative tasks of financing a project TRL 4-6 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Initial Project Scoping phase with pre-feasibility studies Main stakeholders are identified Low municipality capacity to undertake administrative tasks of financing a project TRL 1-3, equal to research
	B. Project risks	Operational risks		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Low complexity: straightforward processes Small-scale maintenance issues, potential failures that can be quickly resolved without significantly affecting the overall project performance Low exposure and vulnerability to climate change impacts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Moderately complex processes Failures could lead to moderate operational disruptions and financial losses Ongoing maintenance for green infrastructure or technology might be more complex or expensive than initially planned 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High degree of vulnerability to climate change impacts of the targeted project Failures could lead to significant operational disruptions and financial losses High exposure to severe weather events, climate change impacts, that can cause significant damage to

Figure 21: Screenshot of the "Readiness and Risk Assessment" module

4.3 Using the Guide

This section explains the use of the Excel-based Guide. The online version on the UP2030 Service Platform will follow the same logic and functionality.

First, users are advised to open the GF Guide in the desktop version of Excel and enable the macros. In the Guide, users are advised to review the "Intro" worksheet where they can find every relevant information about the structure and functionalities of the Guide. Next, they have two options on how to proceed. One option is that they fill out the questions on the Inputs module and then browse the results by clicking on the respective worksheets for each module (or follow the links to those modules on the "Input" worksheet at the bottom of the questionnaire) (see Option A below). As per the second option, they can directly browse and filter the individual modules and if needed, they select the relevant filters directly on the heading (see Option B below).

Key steps of using the GF Guide:

1. **Intro sheet:** Get familiarized with the Guide by reading the introduction for context on UP2030, the purpose of the Guide, and instructions on navigating it.

Option A: Using the Inputs sheet

1. **Inputs sheet:** This is the main interface to filter content across the three core modules:
 - *Financial Instruments*
 - *Case Studies*
 - *International Financing and Technical Assistance Programmes*
2. **Selecting filters on the Inputs sheet:**
 - Select options in grey cells to filter by:
 - **Investment project characterisation:** e.g. sector, climate action type.
 - **Module-specific categories:**
 - For "Financial Instruments" module: type, modality, source, blending category, maturity, readiness & risk.
 - For "Case Studies" module: region, city size, investment size, type of case.
 - For "International Financing and Technical Assistance Programmes" module: type of assistance, EU eligibility.
 - Users must select at least one option in each filter category to generate results.
 - Use the "Select all filters" or "Clear all filters" buttons for quick management.
3. **Applying filters:**
 - Click the "**Filter results**" button. This will hide non-matching entries across the relevant modules.
 - Use quick-access links below the button to jump to filtered data.

Option B: Browsing individual modules

1. **Explore the modules individually:** Users can explore modules directly, by clicking on the respective tabs in the Excel.
2. **Selecting filters in searchable modules:** Use header filters in each searchable worksheet to search or narrow content manually. To see the full database without filters, select all options in the Inputs sheet and apply filters. Non filterable modules can also be accessed directly and browsed freely.

+ Optional step for selecting Readiness & Risk Filter through the "Readiness & Risk Assessment" module

Use this module to:

- Complete a brief questionnaire to score your project's readiness and risk level (1–3).
- Use the result to filter appropriate financial instruments either in the Inputs sheet or directly in the "Financial Instruments" module.

Tips:

- If no results appear, adjust your filters. Keeping other categories broadly selected can help find matches.

- Refer to the "Glossary" sheet for clear definitions of key concepts and terms.
- The modules and filter cells colour-coded modules and filter cells for intuitive navigation.
- Use hyperlinks across modules to explore related instruments, case studies, and stakeholders.
- Macros enable automated filtering, which require the desktop version of Excel. Please download the Guide, open it in the desktop version and allow macros.

Figure 22 shows an example, when the "Inputs" module was used to filter case studies based on user preferences, while Figure 23 shows how the filtered results are shown on the "Case Study" module.

Case studies		
Region	North America	<input type="checkbox"/>
	South America	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Europe	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	Africa	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Asia	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Australia and Oceania	<input type="checkbox"/>
	City size	Multiple cities
Mega (population >2M)		<input type="checkbox"/>
Large (population 0.5M-2M)		<input type="checkbox"/>
Medium (population 0.2M-0.5M)		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Small (population <0.2M)		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Investment size	Large (>300M EUR)	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Medium (50-300M EUR)	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Small (<50M EUR)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Type of case study	Blending instruments	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Innovative financial instruments	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Private finance	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Figure 22: Example of filtering using the "Input" module

CASE STUDIES

#	Name of case study	Location			City size	Project investment size	Climate action type	Trans and
		Region	Country	City				
					Multiple cities, Mega (population >2M), Large (population 0.5M-2M), Medium (population 0.2M-0.5M), Small (population <0.2M)	Large (>300MEUR), Medium (50-300MEUR), Small (<50MEUR)	Climate change mitigation, Climate change adaptation, Climate change mitigation and adaptation	
22	Public-private partnership for a new flood-proof district in Bilbao	Europe	Spain	Bilbao	Medium (population 0.2M-0.5M)	Small (<50M EUR)	Climate change adaptation	
23	Ghent crowdfunding platform realising climate change adaptation projects	Europe	Belgium	Ghent	Medium (population 0.2M-0.5M)	Small (<50M EUR)	Climate change adaptation	

Figure 23: Example of filtered results in the "Case Study" module

4.4 Limitations of the GF Guide

While the Guide in its current form offers a comprehensive overview of financing instruments, case studies, financing programmes and other key information related to municipal climate finance, it has its limitations. First, this Guide aims to help users learn more about the available financing structures and sources and help identify potential solutions that are relevant to the users' needs. However, it does not provide a concrete financing plan or guidance on how to prepare one. Second, after the end of the project, it may run the risk of becoming obsolete as new financing mechanisms and programmes become available, and more practical examples will be able to showcase their use. Additionally, since some of the financing instruments included are new and classified as pilot instruments, there may be a lack of available case studies. This is either because they have not yet been implemented or because implementation is still underway, making it too early to include them in the case studies. Moreover, instruments that are in the pilot stage now may be more widely implemented over the coming years, warranting their updated categorisation into "Emerging". It can also happen that the filtering set on the "Inputs" sheet does not show any results. In this case, users are advised to reset their filters. Finally, the hyperlinks leading to external sources (e.g. case study sources) might not work if the owners of the domain make changes to the structure of the website or make the content unavailable.

5 Integration into the platform and sustainability

5.1 Status of tool integration

The integration of the Guides into the UP2030 Service Platform is currently in progress. The first drafts of the Guides are ready and available on the <https://urbanplanningfor2030.eu/tools>. These are currently demo versions, and some functions might not be available, and bugs can occur. Figure 24 shows the "Tools" page of the UP2030 Service Platform where users can assess the demo version of the Guides. Figure 25 and Figure 26 shows the current format of the two Guide's web-based version on the Platform.

The functionalities and the design of the web-based tools will be finalised and presented at the closing event of the UP2030 project, held in November 2025 in Barcelona. Both the Excel- and web-based tools will be tested with the cities during the event. After integrating the cities' final feedback, the final web-based tools will be finalised by the end of 2025, making them available for cities and other relevant users beyond the UP2030 project.

Figure 24: Screenshot of the UP2030 Service Platform's "Tools" page

UP2030 UP2030 Service Platform ▼ Tools The Project

CBA Guide

What do you want to do? ?

- Getting more familiar with the topic of CBA
- Light approach to CBA for a rough overview of costs and benefits of my project
- Detailed CBA

Are you interested in mitigation or adaptation projects? ?

- Mitigation
- Adaptation
- Mitigation and Adaptation

Which sector would you like to focus on in your activity? ?

- Transport
- Buildings
- Waste Management
- Urban Parks
- Agriculture
- Industry
- Energy

What benefits would you like to include in the CBA? ?

- Health
- Environment
- Cost savings
- Economic and social

What resources are you going to use for the activity? ?

- Internal resources by dedicating staff time
- External resources by mandating an expert

Submit

Figure 25: Screenshot of the CBA Guide's web-based version

The screenshot shows the web-based version of the Green Finance Guide. The header includes the UP2030 logo, 'UP2030 Service Platform' with a dropdown arrow, 'Tools', and 'The Project' button. The main content area is titled 'Green Finance Guide' and 'Investment project characterization'. It features several filter sections:

- Sector** (with a help icon):
 - Transportation and mobility
 - Buildings and energy efficiency
 - Energy generation and systems
 - Water, waste and wastewater
 - Urban development and management
 - Green spaces and nature-based solutions
 - Disaster risk management
- Climate action type** (with a help icon):
 - Climate change mitigation
 - Climate change adaptation
 - Climate change mitigation and adaptation
- Financial instruments** (with a help icon):
 - Instrument type** (with a help icon):
 - Debt
 - Equity
 - Public
 - Grant
 - Risk transfer or mitigation
 - Market based
 - Modality** (with a help icon):
 - Repayable
 - Non-repayable
 - De-risking

Figure 26: Screenshot of the GF Guide's web-based version

5.2 [Next steps](#)

While the Excel-based Guides are considered final at this stage, minor improvements could be made after further consultation with cities before the end of the project. Such discussions are expected during a dedicated session during the closing event of the UP2030 project in Barcelona, in November 2025, where participants will have the opportunity to test the tools and provide feedback. Additionally, cities who did not provide feedback yet could do so by the end of 2025, and their comments, observations will be taken into account.

A visual user manual will be developed by GGGI, in cooperation with ICLEI and the Universitat Internacional de Catalunya (UIC), by the end of 2025. The objective of the user manual will be to facilitate the use of the developed Guides and improve the user experience by providing a pre-recorded video guidance, presenting the Guides' content, key functionalities and structure. The visual manual will be developed for the Massive Open Online Course (MOOC), under the D5.7 - Online Learning Programme materials.

5.3 [Sustainability](#)

To formalise and govern the long-term maintenance and availability of the tools, GGGI will enter into a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) with ICLEI, the owner of the UP2030 Service Platform. The MoU will define the roles and responsibilities of each party, including procedures for updating content

and ensuring that the tools remain relevant, accessible, and technically functional over time. As of the writing of this report the MoU is in drafting phase, with expected finalisation by the end of the project.

Moreover, the GGGI Guides, as part of the overall package offered through the UP2030 Service Platform, will also be made available on the NetZeroCities (NZC) Portal's Knowledge Repository. Their integration will be regulated by the Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) signed in 2025 between Climate-KIC Holding B.V., representing the NZC project, and Fraunhofer Gesellschaft zur Förderung der Angewandten Forschung e.V. on behalf of the UP2030 consortium partners. The specific arrangements for sharing the tools and making them accessible on the Portal, together with other UP2030 project outputs, are currently under discussion between project representatives, with finalisation expected by the end of the project in 2025.

6 Conclusion

The Cost-Benefit Analysis Guide and Green Finance Guide developed under Task 5.3 provide municipalities with practical, user-oriented resources to enhance the financial and economic foundations of their climate actions. By offering guidance on selecting suitable financing instruments and conducting cost-benefit analyses for their projects and initiatives, these tools aim to help cities translate their climate ambitions into bankable, implementable projects.

Their development was strongly informed by the collaboration with UP2030 pilot cities, whose feedback, testing, and insights were instrumental in tailoring the Guides to real urban challenges and decision-making contexts. This co-creation process not only ensured that the tools respond to the practical needs of municipalities but also fostered ownership and capacity among local stakeholders.

Looking beyond the pilot cities, the Guides have the potential to support municipalities across Europe. By providing structured knowledge, case studies, and practical methodologies, they can help a wide range of cities – regardless of size, capacity, or starting point – build stronger investment cases, mobilise diverse financing sources, and advance their Climate City Contracts. At the European level, the Guides contribute to the broader objectives of the Mission for Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities by offering replicable, science-based resources that can be scaled and adapted across contexts.

Made available in an interactive web-based format through the UP2030 Service Platform, and subsequently on the NZC Portal's Knowledge Repository, the Guides will remain accessible beyond the lifetime of the project. In doing so, they represent not only a practical outcome of UP2030 but also a lasting contribution to Europe's urban transformation and climate neutrality agenda.

References

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